

Appendix: Methodological toolbox

Tool no. 3_5_2	
Title	Conservation and Human Use Index (CHUI)
Category	Socio-cultural/Environmental/Spatial (multi-dimensional tool integrating Environment, Governance and Socio-cultural categories)
Purpose of the method	The CHUI identifies and quantifies interactions, conflicts, and synergies between biodiversity conservation and human use of coastal ecosystems. It measures ecological values, ecosystem services, pressures, governance effectiveness, and social perceptions to support evidence-based management and policy decisions.
Effort in time	Effort in time depends on toolbox approach: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Desk-based assessment: ~3 hours (individual expert) • Combined desk-based assessment by stakeholders: ~3 days (including compilation) • Facilitated focus group: ~1 full day (6–8 hours) • Combined approach: 1–2 days (desk preparation + group facilitation)
Number of objects investigated	133 mandatory questions across four main dimensions (a. Natural Values & Ecosystem Services, b. Threats & Pressures, c. Governance, d. Social Perceptions). Additional 19 optional background questions provide context
Data format	Excel file - Numerical (0–3 scoring scale), qualitative (stakeholder perceptions), textual (background descriptions), and graphical (colour-coded grading, Excel outputs).
Description	<p>The Conservation & Human Use Index (CHUI) was developed as a deliverable under the HORIZON project PRO-COAST, titled A PROactive approach for COMmunities to enABle Societal Transformation (2023-2026).</p> <p>The CHUI is a multi-parameter assessment tool designed to identify and track conflicts between biodiversity conservation and ecosystem service overexploitation. It applies the SESF approach to analyse environmental, governance, and social dimensions in Case Study (CS) areas, providing valuable insight between human-environment interactions.</p> <p>The index enables conservation practitioners, local authorities, CS leaders, and stakeholders to conduct a structured and rapid assessment of strengths and weaknesses in governance, ecological conditions, and societal interactions within a given area. Its participatory and flexible nature allows for use across a wide range of settings and supports collaborative, informed decision-making. The tool is designed for periodic use, particularly when evaluating the effectiveness of past management efforts or identifying new challenges.</p> <p>CHUI is fully documented in the CHUI Manual (2025), which provides step-by-step guidance, and is implemented through an Excel-based application that automates scoring, generates colour-</p>

	<p>coded outputs, and produces tailored narrative interpretations. Together, these resources make the CHUI practical and adaptable, supporting use in desk reviews, stakeholder surveys, and facilitated workshops, and enabling managers and stakeholders to identify conflicts, monitor progress over time, and guide conservation and policy responses.</p>
<p>Basic Literature</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ivanić, K-Z., Stolton, S., Figueroa Arango, C. and Dudley, N., 2020. Protected Areas Benefits Assessment Tool + (PA-BAT+): A tool to assess local stakeholder perceptions of the flow of benefits from protected areas. Gland, Switzerland: IUCN. https://doi.org/10.2305/IUCN.CH.2020.PATRS.4.en • Jones, N., Graziano, M., & Dimitrakopoulos, P. G. (2020). Social impacts of European Protected Areas and policy recommendations. <i>Environmental Science & Policy</i>, 112, 134–140. https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envsci.2020.06.016 • Mahajan, S. L., Obiene, S., Ojwang, L., Olwero, N., Valdivia, A., Wosu, A., Adrid, E., Andradi-Brown, D. A., Andriamalala, G., & Ban, N. C. (2023). Introducing Elinor for monitoring the governance and management of area-based conservation. <i>Conservation Biology</i>, 38(2), e14213. https://doi.org/10.1111/cobi.14213 • Ostrom, E. (2009). A general framework for analyzing sustainability of social-ecological systems. <i>Science</i>, 325(5939), 419–422. • Vayanou, Ph., Georgiou, P., Kounnamas, C. (2025). Conservation & Human Use Index. Under PRO-COAST: A PROactive approach for COMmunities to enABle Societal Transformation (2023–2026).
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<p>Linked material</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Conservation_HumanUse_Index_v10 • Conservation&HumanUse Index_Manual_v1